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HYPOGLYCAEMIC EFFECT OF GILO (*Tinospora cordifolia*): A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Diabetes Mellitus is one of the common metabolic disorders characterized by persistent hyperglycemia caused by absolute or relative insulin deficiency, causing abnormalities of carbohydrates, proteins & lipid metabolism and significant & significant disturbance of water, electrolytes. According to WHO the worldwide prevalence of Diabetes mellitus was estimated to be 422 million in 2014 and is projected to rise up to 750 million by the year 2030. Oral hypoglycaemic agents like sulphonylureas & biguanides are still the major players in the management of the disease but there is growing interest in herbal remedies due to the side effects associated with oral hypoglycaemic agents. Unani Physicians were very much familiar to the symptoms and complication of the disease. *Ibne Sina* in his book *Al Qanoon* has described about the symptoms like polydipsia, polyuria and mentioned gangrene among its complication. The Unani herbal medicine have been the highly esteemed source of medicine throughout human history. Unani System of Medicine deals with several means of treatment like Ilaj bil Ghiza (dietotherapy), Ilaj bil Dawa (Pharmacotherapy) & Ilaj bil Tadbeer (Regimenal Therapy), that can be aided as an adjuvant therapies. Where as in Classical Unani literature recommendations of diets & exercise along with various compound formulations and single drugs are being used from ancient time such as Safoofe Ziabetus, Qurs Ziabetus Khas, Qurs Tabasheer, Safoofe Hindi, & Kachnar (*Bauhina variegata*), Gilo (*Tinospora cordifolia*), Tukhme Methi or Hulbah (*Trigonella foenum-graecum*), Klonji (*Nigella sativa*), Tukhme Hyat (*Witania coagulans*), Tukhme Karela (*Momordica charantia*), Gurmar Booti (*Gymnemma sylvestre*), Talhab (*Spirulina platensis*). The outcome of these medication is proved to have a hypoglycaemic effect and these can be used along with the dietotherapy in present scenario to reduce the risk of complications. This review paper will discuss the potential of hypoglycaemic effect of Gilo (*Tinospora cordifolia*) in Diabetes Mellitus.

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INTRODUCTION

Gilo is a well known drug in Unani medicine. *Gilo* (*Tinospora cordifolia*), also called Guduchi is an herbaceous vine of the family Menispermaceae indigenous to the tropical areas of India, Myanmar & Sri Lanka. The plant is a climbing shrub growing in deciduous and dry forest. *Gilo* was included in the Bengal pharmacopoeia of 1844 and the Indian pharmacopoeia of 1868.[1] The *Satte Gilo* (starch) is obtained from the roots and stems of the plant are similar to arrow-root in appearance and effect. The leaves are heart shaped. The succulent bark is creamy white to grey in color, with deep clefts spotted with lenticels. It is used in the treatment of various diseases, particularly common fever, malarial fever, Diabetes, cuts and wounds.

Botanical Name:-

Tinospora cordifolia[2],[3],[4],[5],[6],[7],[8],[9]

Family:-

Menispermaceae[2],[3],[4],[5],[6],[7],[8],[9]

Distribution:-

Found throughout tropical India, [10] Myanmar, Andaman and Ceylon. Ascending to the altitude of 900 meter. It is also distributed in Myanmar, Andaman & Ceylon.[10],[11]

Vernacular Names:-[1],[2],[3],[7],[12],[13]

Arabic:	Gilo
Assamese:	Siddhilate, Amarlata
Bengali:	Gulanca, Giloe, Gurach, Gadanca, Guluncha, Ningilo, Golanca
Bombay:	Ambravel, Gharol, Giroli, Guloe, Gulwel
Burmese:	Singomoni
Ceylon:	Chintil
China:	K`uan chu Hsing
Deccan:	Gulbel, Gulo
English:	Gulanca Tinospora
French:	Culanca
Goa:	Amritvel
Gujarati:	Galac, Garo, Gado, Gulo, Gulwel
Hindi:	Ambarvel, Giloe, Gurcha, Gurach, Gulanca, Gubel, Gurudvel, Gulvel
Kannada:	Amrutoballi, Amrulballi, Madhuparne, Uganiballi
Kashmiri:	Amrita, Gilo, Bark
Kumaon:	Gulanca, Guracha
Malayalam:	Amrytu, Peyamarytam, Sittamrytu
Marathi:	Ambarvel, Gharol, Giroli, Gulvel, Guloe
Mumbai:	Ambarvel, Giroli
Nepali:	Gurjo
Persian:	Gulbel
Punjabi:	Batindu, Gilo, Garham, Garum, Gilo-Gularish
Sanskrit:	Amrita, Amritalata, Chakrangi, Dhira, Guluchi, Kundalli
Sikkim:	Gurjo
Sindhi:	Sutgilo
Tamil:	Amridavalli, Kaipruchindil, Chindal, Seendal, Sindil Silam, Kodi, Amudam, Asasi, Kunali, Sadi,
Telugu:	Thippateega, Guduchi, Madhuka, Manpala, Somida
Urdu:	Gilo
Uriya:	Guluchi, Gulochi, Gulanca

Mahiyat (Morphology):-**Botanical Description:-**

Gilo is succulent glabrous deciduous climbing shrub peeling of ash coloured bark. The flowers are small and yellow or greenish-yellow in colour. The fruits are small and red in color. It puts out long, slender aerial roots, often growing on mango or neem trees.

Stem & Bark:-

The stem is succulent, croky and grooved with long pendulous filiform fleshy aerial roots from the branches. The bark is grey brown or creamy white & warty. [14]

Leaves:-

The leaves are membranous, simple, alternate, extipulate, membranous and 7-8 nerved & 5-10 cm or rarely 12cm x 10 cm long. Leaves are roundish or subdeltoid, cordate with broad sinus & basal lobes. There is reticulate venation with microscopic glistening glands beneath 2.5-7.0 cm long. [1], [14]

Flowers:-

The flowers are small and yellow or greenish-yellow in color, growing in lax racemes from nodes on old wood. There are axillary and terminal racemes or racemose panicles. Flowering in April. The male flowers are lustered & female flowers are usually solitary. [1],[14]

Sepals:-

The sepals are three in outer side & three in inner side. The outer sepals are very small, ovate-oblong & acute. The inner sepals are larger, membranous broadly elliptical, concave, 34 mm & yellow.

Petals:-

The petals are six in number, equal, about 2mm long & broadly spatulate. Each petal is loosely embracing a stamen. The lamina is triquetrous or subtrilobed & relaxed at apex.

Fruit:-

The fruits are drupe, ovoid, glossy, succulent, pea-sized and red coloured on ripe. [1],[14]

Macroscopic Studies

Macroscopically the stems are succulent, soft, possessing long, filiform, aerial root arising from branches. Bark warty, creamish white or grey brown; wood soft, perforated. Dried sample consists of 5 to 10cm long conical pieces, light in weight; bark light and papery, brittle, dark brown; wood with longitudinal surface ridges, and radially divided into wedge shaped pieces in cross-sections. Pieces difficult to fracture when fully dried and can be torn only by twisting; odourless; taste bitter. [15]

Microscopic Studies

Transverse section shows cork, cortex and vasculature. The cork tissue is broken at some places due to tenticle cortex is wide. The outer zone of cortex consists of 3 to 5 rows of irregularly arranged tangentially elongated chlorenchymatous cell. Several secretory cells found scattered in the cortex. Vascular zone is composed of discrete vascular strands, with 10 to 12 or more wedge shaped strip of phloem, alternating with wide medullary rays. [16]

Seeds:-

The seeds are curved. [1],[14]

Parts Used:-

Leaf, Stem & fecula, Stem bark and Root. [2],[10],[13],[17],[18]

Mizaj (Temperament):-

Har1(Hot) Yabis1(Dry)

Har1(Hot) Ratab1(Wet) Murakkabul Quwa

Af'al (Pharmacological Actions):-

1. *Dafae Bukhar* (Antipyretic)[1],[3],[5],[9],[13],[22]
2. *Musakkine Alam* (Analgesic)[9],[5],[22]
3. *Muqawie Bah* (Aphrodisiac)[1],[5],[7],[17],[19],[20],[22],[24],[25]
4. *Qabiz* (Astringent)[1],[5],[12],[26]
5. *Mudirre Baol* (Diuretic)[1],[2],[3],[4],[12],[21]
6. *Dafae Suaale* (Antitussive)[19],[25]
7. *Kasire Riyah* (Carminative)[20]
8. *Dafe Atshak* (Antisyphilitic) [2],[5][11],[12],[14],[26]
9. *Dafae Sozak* (Useful in gonorrhoea)[5],[6],[13],[21],[23],[24],[25],[26]
10. *Ma'ane Naubat* (Antiperiodic)[1],[2],[5],[15],[19],[20],[21]
11. *Mussaffie Dam* (Blood purifier)[12],[14],[21],[25],[26]
12. *Qatile Kirmeshikam* (Antihelminthic)[12],[13],[21],[26]
13. *Mukhrije Balgham*[20]
14. *Muqawwie Meda*[12],[21],[26]
15. *Mushtahi* (Appetizer)[20],[24]
16. *Muhallile Awram* (Anti-inflammatory)[5],[9],[12],[13],[25]
17. *Mowallide Mani* (Spermatogouge)[20],[24]
18. *Mudire Haiz* (Amenogouge)[21]
19. *Dafa-e-ghashi* (Anti fainting)[1],[3],[5],[9],[13],[22]
20. *Naf-e-ziabetes* (Antidiabetic) [1],[3],[5],[9],[13]
21. *Dafa-e-Sozish meda* (Antacid) [1],[3],[5],[9],[13]

Mawaqe-e-Istemaal (Therapeutic Uses):-

1. *Tape Damwi* [19],[20]
2. *Tape Safrawi* [19],[20],[24]
3. *Alam*[5],[13],[19],[25]
4. *Zo'fe Bah*[17],[20],[24]
5. *Aatshak*[2],[5],[11],[13],[14]
6. *Sozaak*[5],[6],[7],[21],[23],[24]
7. *Bawaaseer*[1],[3],[5],[13],[20]
8. *Yarqaan*[1],[5],[6],[13],[20],[24],[25]
9. *Kirme Shikam*[17],[21],[1],[12]
10. *Is'hale Muzmin*[1],[5],[7],[12],[13],[20],[23],[26]
11. *Qillate Mani*[20],[24]
12. *Hararate Jigar*[24]
13. *Ghashi*[20],[24]
14. *Hirqatul Baol*[21]
15. *Shozishe Dil wa Jigar*[19]
16. *Niqris*[2],[4],[5],[13],[22]
17. *Zo'fe Ishteha*[20],[24]
18. *Su'aal* (Cough) [1],[3],[5],[9],[13]
19. *Ziabetes Shakri* (Diabetes mellitus) [20], [21], [24]
20. *Qillat-e-Ishtiha* (Anorexia) [1],[5],[6],[13],[20],[24],[25]

Ethnobotanical Actions:-

1. Hypoglycaemic[1],[3],[4],[5],[13],[18],[22]
2. Hypocholesterolimic[4]
3. Immunostimulant [4],[5],[13]
4. Tonic[1],[3],[4],[5],[6],[11],[14],[19],[25],[27]
5. Antiinflammatory[9],[22],[27]
6. Antacid[19],[22]
7. Antioxidant[4],[5]
8. Deobstruent[5]
9. Antibacterial [5],[13]
10. Antiallergic[4]
11. Alterative[5],[27]
12. Antispasmodic[5],[27]
13. Antiviral[5]
14. Antiulcer[4]
15. Stimulant[27]
16. Bronchodialator[4]
17. Lipolytic[5]
18. Nutritious[19]
19. Hepatoprotective[5]

Ethnobotanical Uses:-

1. Fever[1], [2],[3],[12],[13],[18],[23],[27]
2. Intermittent fever[2],[11]
3. Diabetes[1],[3],[4],[5],[13],[18],[27][28]
4. Debility[1],[2],[11],[13],[14]
5. Dyspepsia[1],[2],[13],[15]
6. Anemia[3],[5],[13]
7. Diarrhea[19],[20]
8. Cough[2],[3],[4],[13],[19],[20],[24]
9. Dysentery[1],[5],[7],[12],[13],[23]
10. Dysuria[5],[13]
11. Erysipelas[1],[4],[5],[13]
12. Escherichia[4],[5],[13]
13. Fracture[4],[13]
14. Giddiness[13]
15. Inflammation[9],[12],[22],[27]
16. Nausea[4],[5],[13],[14]
17. Vomiting[3],[13]
18. Rheumatism[1],[4],[5],[6],[11],[15],[23]
19. Leucorrhoea[4],[18],[27]
20. Stress[4],[13]
21. Hypertension[1]
22. Snake bite[3],[5],[11],[13]
23. Tuberculosis[5],[13],[20]
24. Spermatorrhoea[5],[18]
25. Filariasis[13]

Miqdar-e- Khuraq (Dose):-

Up to 2 Masha of Satte Gilo or 4-9 gm Decoction [19]

Muzir Asrat (Adverse Effects):-

Various Unani physicians stated that *Gilo* has almost no side effect[20] except *Muqi*. [21]

Musleh (Correctives):-

If any side effect occurs then it may be suppressed by using *Tabasheer* and *Dana Heel*. [19],[20],[21]

Taste:- Bitter[19]

Badal (Substitute): *Gilo*, *Sat-e-Gilo* [19],[20]

Murakkabat (Compound Formulation):-

Arqe Badawar Shikai[17]
 Arqe Gilo[17],[31]
 Fawakehe Satte Gilo[30]
 Lauq Sapistan[29],[30]
 Lauq Motadil[29]
 Safoofe Ziabetes[30]
 Safoofe Satte Gilo[17]

Keemiyai Ajza (Chemical constituents):-

A variety of constituents have been isolated from *Tinospora cordifolia* plant and their structures were elucidated. They belong to different classes such as alkaloids, diterpenoid lactones, terpenoid lactones, glycosides, steroids, sesquiterpenoid, phenolics, aliphatic compounds and polysaccharides.[2],[7],[13],[14] The stem contains alkaloidal constituents, including berberine; bitter principles, including berbrin, columbin, chasmenthin, palmerin, tinosporin, tinosporol, tinosporid, tinosporon, tinosporic acid, tinosporidine, columbin, chasmanthin, giloin, giloin1,2-substituted pyrrolidine, norclerodanediterpene-O-glicoside, cordifolide, unosporin cordifol, cordifolone, magnoflorine, tembitarine, cordifoliosides A and tinosporol. Leaves of this plant are rich in protein (11.2%) & are fairly rich in calcium & phosphorus.[2],[7],[13],[14]

DISCUSSION

There are certain scientific reports which show the mechanism of hypoglycaemic actions of *Tinospora cordifolia*, in various drug dosage form.

Scientific Reports**Hypoglycaemic activity:-**

The methanol extract of *Tinospora cordifolia* stem was found to exhibit a signifying hypoglycaemic and antioxidant activity in alloxan induced diabetic rats.[32] Oral administration of the water extract of *Tinospora cordifolia* root caused a significant reduction in blood glucose, brain lipid level, hepatic glucose-6-phosphatase, serum acid phosphatase, alkaline and lactate dehydrogenase and increase in body weight, total haemoglobin and hepatic hexokinase in alloxanized diabetic rats.[33]

Tinospora cordifolia shows hypoglycaemic activity possibly by stimulating endogenous insulin secretion by altering the cell membrane permeability. [34]

The petroleum ether extract of *Tinospora cardifolia* stem administered to rats significantly decreased the glucose, triglycerides and body weight, and increased the HDL-cholesterol levels. [35]

Compound tinosporaside isolated from the n-butanol fraction of the stem of *T.cordifolia* exhibited significant antihyperglycemic activity in streptozotocin-model which is comparable to metformin.[36] Various studies demonstrate amelioration of experimental diabetic neuropathy and gastropathy in rats, reduction of blood sugar in alloxan-induced hyperglycemic rats and rabbits, significant reduction in blood glucose and brain lipids, increase in glucose tolerance in rodents, increase in glucose metabolism, inhibitory effect on adrenaline-induced hyperglycemia by pyrrolidine derivative, and significant hypoglycaemic effect in normal and alloxan diabetic rabbits following administration of *T. cordifolia*.[37],[38],[39],[40]

Anti Allergic Activity:-

In a clinical study, 100% relief was reported from sneezing in 83% of the patients on treatment with *T. cordifolia*,. Thus *T. cordifolia* significantly decreased all symptoms of allergic rhinitis and was well tolerated.[41]

Cardioprotective Activity:-

A dose-dependent reduction in infarct size and in serum and heart lipid peroxide levels were observed with prior treatment with *T. cordifolia* in ischemia-reperfusion induced myocardial infarction in rats.[42]

The stem extract has been normalize alterations in the lipid metabolism caused by diabetes mellitus in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats indirectly benefiting the heart.[43]

Hepatoprotective:-

The hepatoprotective action of *T. cordifolia* was reported in one of the experiment in which goats treated with *T. cordifolia* have shown significant clinical and hematobiochemical improvement in CCl4 induced hepatopathy. Extract of *T. cordifolia* has also exhibited *in vitro* inactivating property against Hepatitis B and E surface antigen in 48-72 Hours.[44]

Anti-stress and tonic property:-

The anti-stress and tonic property of the plant was clinically tested and it was found that it brought about good response in children with moderate degree of behaviour disorders and mental deficit. It has also significantly improved the I.Q. levels. [45]

Antispasmodic:-

The aqueous extract of the stem antagonizes the effect of agonists such as 5 hydroxytryptamine, histamine, bradykinin and prostaglandins E1 and E2 on the rabbit smooth muscle, relaxes the intestinal, uterine smooth muscle and inhibits the constrictor response of histamine and acetylcholine on smooth muscle. [45]

Anti-inflammatory:-

The alcoholic extract of *T. cordifolia* has been found to exert anti-inflammatory actions in models of acute and subacute inflammation.[46]

Antineoplastic Activity:-

Intraperitoneal injection of the alcoholic extract of *T. cordifolia* has been shown to Dalton's lymphoma (DL) bearing mice stimulated macrophage functions like phagocytosis, antigen-presenting ability and secretion of Interleukin-1 (IL-1), tumour necrosis factor (TNF) and Reference Nutrient Intake (RNI) as well as slowed tumor growth and increased lifespan of the tumor-bearing host.[47]

Osteoprotective Activity:-

Rats treated with *T. cordifolia* showed an osteoprotective effect, as the bone loss in tibiae was slower than that in controls. Serum osteocalcin and cross-laps levels were significantly reduced. This study demonstrates that extract of *T. cordifolia* has the potential for being used as antiosteoporotic agent.[48]

Antifertility Activity:-

Oral administration of 70% methanolic extract of *T. cordifolia* stem to male rats at a dose level of 100 mg/d for 60 days did not cause body weight loss but decreased the weight of testes, epididymis, seminal vesicle and ventral prostate in a significant manner.[49]

Anti Ulcer Activity:-

Treatment with a formulation containing *T. cordifolia* has been shown to reduce ulcer index total acidity, with an increase in the pH of gastric fluid in pylorus-ligated rats and in the ethanol-induced gastric mucosal injury in rats.[50]

Anti Leprotic Activity:-

T. cordifolia is used for its *kushtahara* (anti-leprotic) properties, along with wide use in *kandu* and *visarpa* (types of skin disorders) and has been shown to exert antileprotic activity in a combination formulation.[51]

Diuretic Activity:-

In a scientific study on rats and human volunteers, *T. cordifolia* was found to have diuretic effects.[52] It was also found effective in modulation of morphology and some gluconeogenic enzymes activity in diabetic rat kidney. [53]

CONCLUSION

Unani herbal medicines plays important role in the management of Diabetes. Besides the fundamental importance of this pharmacotherapeutic methodology there is a problem of lack of uniform standardisation. It therefore apparently seems essential to standardize them and to develop certain scientific parameters for evaluation of the efficacy of these drugs as it is cost effective, user friendly devoid of adverse effects. Hence scientific studies are being under taken to validate these age old drugs in different Unani research institutions of India so that the benefits may be reaped by large section of society.

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